

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Tomato Consumption in the CIS Countries: Dynamics and Prospects

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Tomato Consumption Trends

Tomatoes are one of the most popular vegetables in the CIS countries, playing a key role both in the daily diet of the population and in processing for the food industry. They are used not only in fresh form, but also for the production of sauces, pastas, and canned food, which makes the market especially significant on a regional scale.

The "Values/Volume" field shows the consumption of tomatoes in the CIS countries in the period from 2018 to 2030 (million tons). According to data from Statista Market Insights (June 2025), the dynamics of consumption in the CIS is characterized by relative stability. In the period from 2018 to 2021, there were small fluctuations, after which the market entered a smooth growth trajectory. By 2030, consumption is projected to increase from 9.5–10 million tons to 11–11.5 million tons.

This growth is due to both population growth and the preservation of traditional culinary habits, in which the tomato occupies a central place.

Average Consumption per Capita

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Fig 1. The "Values/Volume" field shows the consumption of fertilizers in the CIS countries in the period from 2018-2030

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Fig 1. The field "Average consumption per capita" shows the apparent consumption of tomatoes in the CIS countries in the period from 2018-2030

In 2018-2019, the average figure was kept at about 40 kg per year per person, but in 2021-2022 there was a noticeable decline to 37 kg. This decrease is due to price fluctuations

and economic factors that limit the purchasing power of the population. Nevertheless, starting in 2023, the situation is gradually changing: consumption is growing, and by 2030 it is projected to reach the level of 43-44 kg per person per year. This result indicates a recovery in consumer demand and a strengthening of the role of tomatoes in the diet.

In the future, the tomato market in the CIS will develop towards an increase in production and consumption. The key drivers of growth will be the improvement of greenhouse technologies, the expansion of the range of processed products and the growing popularity of environmentally friendly and organic products. At the same time, given the high elasticity of demand for vegetables, the market will remain sensitive to macroeconomic factors and price fluctuations.

Thus, tomatoes in the CIS continue to be a basic necessity product, the demand for which is stable even in times of crisis. In the long term, we can expect not only an increase in domestic consumption, but also an expansion of export potential, especially to the countries of the Middle East and Asia.

Foreign Trade in Tomatoes in the CIS: analysis based on Trademark data (2024)

The tomato market in the CIS countries is characterized not only by domestic production and consumption, but also by active participation in foreign trade. According to Trademark data for 2024, the total import of tomatoes by the countries of the region amounted to about \$ 604 million, which is only a small part of the global figure of \$ 12.2 billion. Exports, on the contrary, reached \$354 million, which is also a moderate share of the global total of \$12.4 billion. Thus, the region remains rather a net importer, but individual countries demonstrate competitiveness in foreign markets.

The largest importer in the CIS is Russia, which accounts for over \$391 million. This is more than half of the region's total imports and almost two thirds of its volume. Thus, the Russian market remains a key driver of demand, forming the basis for export supplies both inside and outside the CIS. The second largest importer is Ukraine with an indicator of 113.6 million dollars, followed by Kazakhstan (57.1 million) and Belarus (16 million).

Imports to Armenia, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan are significantly lower, while Tajikistan occupies a marginal position вЂ“ only 151 thousand dollars.

If we consider exports, Azerbaijan is the leader in the region, supplying tomatoes worth over 175 million dollars. This is half of all CIS exports, reflecting the successful development of the greenhouse industry and its geographical proximity to high-demand markets. Uzbekistan ranks second (\$66.5 million), which is actively developing export channels, primarily to Russia and Kazakhstan. This is followed by Turkmenistan (52.9 million) and Armenia (33.2 million). Against this background, Russia’s exports look symbolic of only 856 thousand dollars, which confirms its dependence on imports.

Interestingly, a number of countries in the region (for example, Ukraine, Belarus and Kazakhstan) simultaneously appear as importers and exporters. Their export figures are relatively small, from \$289,000 for Belarus to \$24.6 million for Kazakhstan, which indicates re-export or niche supplies rather than a large-scale presence on the world market.

Thus, the structure of foreign trade in tomatoes in the CIS demonstrates a pronounced asymmetry: Russia is the largest importer and consumer, while Azerbaijan and Uzbekistan are key exporters. This complementarity forms a kind of "CIS internal market where commodity flows are distributed depending on climatic conditions and investment activity in greenhouse technologies.

In the future, we can expect further growth in exports from the countries of the South Caucasus and Central Asia, while maintaining steady demand in the Russian market. This creates opportunities for expanding interregional cooperation, as well as stimulating competition with traditional tomato suppliers to Europe and the Middle East.

THE WORLD’S LARGEST TOMATO EXPORTERS IN 2024

The market for fresh and chilled tomatoes in 2024 demonstrated a steady concentration of exports in the hands of a limited number of countries. Mexico remains the leader by a huge margin, with exports totaling more than \$3.3 billion. This result is due to its

proximity to the world's largest market, the United States of America, as well as large-scale investments in greenhouse production and modern logistic

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The second place is occupied by the Netherlands (about \$ 1.9 billion), which is not only a producer, but also a major logistics hub for the re-export of tomatoes within the European Union. Morocco occupies the third position (about \$ 1.7 billion), which has significantly strengthened its position in recent years due to favorable climatic conditions and the diversification of sales markets in Europe.

This is followed by Spain (about 1.1 billion dollars) and France (700 million), which traditionally act as important suppliers for the European market. Canada and the United States occupy average positions with exports in the range of \$ 600 million and \$400-500 million, respectively, due to high domestic demand and limited volumes for foreign trade.

Among other countries, Turkey and Belgium are notable, each of which exported about \$ 400 million, as well as Italy with a more modest result of about \$ 250 million. Thus, the global structure of tomato exports remains quite concentrated: the three leading players Mexico, the Netherlands and Morocco control more than half of the global market. At the same time, the dynamics of recent years shows the growing role of the countries of North Africa and the Eastern Mediterranean, which are gradually increasing competition with traditional European producers.

Conclusion If we compare the CIS with the global picture, the difference in scale becomes obvious. In 2024, global exports of fresh and chilled tomatoes reached \$12.4 billion. Thus, the CIS remains a relatively modest player in the global tomato trade. The region is more focused on domestic consumption, while world leaders are building their strategy on large-scale exports. Nevertheless, the CIS countries, especially Azerbaijan and Uzbekistan, have the potential to strengthen their positions due to the growing demand in Europe and the Middle East, which makes the development of greenhouse production and logistics key areas for future growth.

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